

OPTIMIZATION OF ORTHOPEDIC-DENTAL CARE FOR PUPILS OF SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS FOR CHILDREN WITH MENTAL DISABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Oral health is an important component of every person's physical, mental and social well-being. Today, caries and periodontal disease remain the most common dental diseases not only among adults, but also among younger populations throughout the world. According to recent epidemiological studies conducted on healthy children, the incidence of dental pathology is high, with the prevalence of caries among healthy age groups 12–15 years being 63.3–83 years, 4% and 81.7–88.7%, intensity 3.02 -3.75 and 4.6-5.73, and the prevalence of periodontal tissue diseases in the group of healthy 12-year-old children ranged from 37.8% to 50%, in the 15-year-old group of children it ranged from 57.7% to 84.7%.

The prevalence of caries is also high in children with mental retardation of preschool and school age, while the intensity of caries is higher in children aged 13–18 years with mild mental retardation (MID). These indicators increase with age and depend on the severity of the underlying disease.

We have implemented a program for the prevention of dental diseases in children with disabilities, but most of them were focused on children with mild and moderate mental retardation, where we will take into account not only the degree of mental retardation, but also teaching them oral care skills and diet child.

Purpose of the study: Increasing the efficiency of providing therapeutic and preventive dental care to children with mental retardation based on the implementation of a program for the prevention of dental diseases, taking into account their limited capabilities in the Samarkand region.

Research objectives:

1. To study the actual state of the organization of dental care for children with mental retardation living in orphanages in the Samarkand region.
2. To study the level of dental morbidity in children with mental retardation living in orphanages and to identify its dependence on some external factors (Samarkand region).
3. Conduct a microbiological study of dental plaque to assess the risk of developing dental diseases in mentally retarded children.
4. To analyze the dynamics of the intensity of caries during the 3rd year in mentally retarded children suffering from Down syndrome
5. Develop and implement a program for the prevention of dental diseases for mentally retarded children living in an orphanage, taking into account their limited health capabilities, using a differentiated approach to teaching oral hygiene.

Material and research methods.

This study was conducted in specialized schools for mentally retarded children No. 1 and No. 62, located in the Samarkand region, a specialized boarding school for mentally retarded children of the Kattakurgan district No. 5 and a specialized school for mentally retarded children No. 63 of the Akdarya district - including between 6, 9 and 12-year-old boarding school students, among whom the hygienic state of the oral cavity, dental caries and tissue periodontal disease were studied and a special program for the prevention of dental diseases, aimed at children with intellectual disabilities, was applied. Depending on the age, gender, diet, type of major neurological diseases, the presence of Down syndrome and the degree of socialization of children accepted as part of the study, the state of the oral apparatus is studied, a special program applied for a certain period of time aimed at the prevention of dental diseases, the level of dental diseases is determined. their effectiveness. The following indicators were assessed: prevalence of caries; intensity of caries of permanent teeth according to the KPU index; the clinical condition of periodontal tissues was assessed using the PMA index as modified by Parma (1960). The hygienic condition of the mouth was assessed using the simplified hygiene index IGR-U according to Green - Vermillion (1964).

In the groups of 6, 12 and 15 year old children, the distribution was as follows: subgroup 1 (socialized children + conditionally free food) included 22, 40 and 45 children aged 6, 12 and 15 years, respectively; to subgroup 2 (unsocialized children + regulated nutrition) – 15, 36 and 28 children aged 6, 12 and 15 years, respectively. In these subgroups, an assessment of oral hygiene (IGR-U) and the condition of periodontal tissues (PMA) were carried out.

Results:

It is known from the literature that children with Down syndrome are less at risk of developing dental caries, therefore, within subgroups with different socialization, a division was made taking into account the presence of this syndrome. Thus, within the subgroups of 6, 12 and 15-year-old socialized children, children who do not have Down syndrome were identified - 10, 32 and 40 children, respectively, and children suffering from this syndrome - 12, 8 and 5 children, respectively. Among 6, 12 and 15-year-old unsocialized children, subgroups of children without Down syndrome were also identified - 11, 30 and 15 children, respectively, and children with Down syndrome - 4, 6 and 13 children, respectively. In these subgroups, the prevalence and intensity of caries was assessed.

To assess the risk of developing dental diseases, a microbiological study of dental plaque was carried out, for which children from subgroup 1 in the amount of 23 people and from subgroup 2 - 21 people were randomly selected. To conduct a microbiological study, supragingival plaque was collected by scraping with a sterile excavator No. 2.

The third stage of our research was the development, implementation and evaluation of the effectiveness of a program for the prevention of dental diseases adapted for mentally retarded children in preschool conditions.

The prevention program included teaching children oral hygiene and health education work with the staff of the institution and the parents of some of the students who attended the boarding school. Individual methods of prevention were also carried out: professional hygiene, application of fluoride-containing varnish to the teeth, sealing of fissures .

The effectiveness of the implemented adapted prevention program, which takes into account the medical, psychological and pedagogical characteristics of children, was assessed by the hygiene index (IGR-U) and the condition of periodontal tissues (PMA index) initially, 1, 2, 3 years after the start of training.

Data obtained from 9- and 12-year-old children before the implementation of the program served as internal controls for groups of children who entered the prevention program at the ages of 6-8 and 9-11 years. At the same time, the group of 9-year-old children is a comparison group for the other groups of 9-year-olds and becomes the main group three years after these children reach the age of 12. For children who entered the prevention program at the age of 12 years, 15-year-old previously examined children served as a control group

The prevalence and intensity of dental caries in mentally retarded children depended on socialization, which determined lifestyle and diet, as well as on the presence of Down syndrome.

The incidence of dental caries in mentally retarded children living in orphanages depends on their socialization, which determines some features of their lifestyle and diet. The risk group consists of socialized children without Down syndrome: the prevalence of caries was 31.0, 62.0 and 83.0% with an intensity of 0[0;1.17], 2[0;4], 4[3;5] in 6 , 12, 15 year old children, respectively. In unsocialized children without Down syndrome, the prevalence of dental caries was low - 0, 18.0 and 22.5% in 6, 12 and 15 year olds, respectively, and children with Down syndrome had no dental caries. In socialized children, mild gingivitis predominated (55, 50 and 50% among 6, 12 and 15 year old children, respectively), in unsocialized children - moderate gingivitis (47.1 and 41.6% in 6 and 15 year old children, respectively) and severe (38.6% in 12-year-olds). 45[26;67.5]. The inability to independently properly care for their mouth makes this group of children especially vulnerable to periodontal disease.

Conclusions:

A differentiated approach to teaching oral hygiene, based on the possibility of developing self-care skills in mentally retarded children, taking into account their mental and physical capabilities, can significantly improve oral hygiene and the condition of periodontal tissues. In the first training group, there was a decrease in the PMA index from 15%[0;25.6] to 0%[0;

2.6], in group II - from 14% [0; 29] to 0%[0; 4], in group III with 35% [15.1; 64.5] to 6%[0; eleven]. The prevalence of children with healthy periodontium increased from 19% to 56.5%.

Over the three years of implementation of the prevention program, the reduction in the increase in the hygiene index was 71.0% in training group I (independent care and staff supervision), 65.7% in training group II (independent care and staff assistance) and 70.0% in group III (staff departure). In 9, 12 and 15-year-old socialized children, the prevalence of caries after three years was 13.5, 43.4 and 63% with an intensity of 0[0;0], 0.5[0;4], 3[0;4, 5], respectively, which is lower than the control group (42.9, 60 and 76% at intensity 0[0;3.25], 3[0;4.5], 4[1.5;5], respectively).

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